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Building blocks for resilience in evolving ICT systems

Certifying the Security and Resilience of Supply Chain Services

D2.1: Supply Chain Analysis and Requirements

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Revision History

Version	Date	By	Overview
0.11	18/1/2021	All WP2 partners	Tentative ToC, unifying previous proposals
0.2	25/01/2021	CRF	Final ToC
0.2	26/02/2021	MAG, CRF, UNSPMF, FP, CLS, STS, SU, TSI, PN	First contributions provided
0.3	01/03/2021	CRF	Integration of contributions from the partners
0.3.1	09/03/2021	CRF	Minor modifications
0.3.1	19/03/2021	MAG, CRF, UNSPMF, FP, CLS, SU, VPF, HYPER	Update and integration to first contribution
0.4	25/03/2021	CRF	Integration of contributions from the partners
0.4.1	26/03/2021	CRF	Minor modifications
0.4.2	09/04/2021	MAG, CRF	Minor modifications
0.5	10/05/2021	CRF	Integration of contributions
0.5.1	13/05/2021	CRF, MAG, UBI, UNSPMF	Last contributions and modifications added before internal review
0.6	28/05/2021	CRF	Updated version incorporating input and comments from internal reviewers
1.0	31/05/2021	CRF	Final version

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List of Acronyms

Acronym	Description
AIS	Automatic identification system
BP	Business Partner
CA	Conformity Assessment
CC	Common Criteria
CII	Critical Information Infrastructure
CSA	Cybersecurity Act
ENS	Entry Summary Declaration
LNG	Liquefied Natural Gas
MRA	Mutual Recognition Agreement
PCS	Port Community System
PDCA	Plan-Do-Check-Act
RA	Risk Assessment
SC	Supply Chain
SCADA	Supervisory Control And Data Acquisition
SCRM	Supply Chain Risk Management
SCM	Standard Cargo Manifest
SCS	Supply Chain Service
SOG-IS	Senior Officials Group Information Systems Security
ToE	Target of Evaluation
TVRA	Threat Vulnerability Risk Analysis
VTS	Vehicle Transport Service

Executive Summary

The objective of this deliverable is to report the results of the activities performed in the first phase of CYRENE's Work Package 2. The main output is related to the requirements that have been collected from relevant standards and literature review, project pilot partners, as well as external stakeholders.

The document can be divided in four main parts. In the first one, an overview of the Supply Chains is given, describing both their classification, including three different views (business, technical and sectorial) of the SCs, and their security aspects, consisting of the threat landscape, legal framework, SC security and Risk Management standards and SC risk assessment methodology and tools.

In the second part, an overview of the EU Certification schemes is provided, encompassing the general definition and requirements (policy, legal, standards, methodologies, technical) regarding the security certification.

Moreover, in the third part, the document reports on the methodology used for collecting, analyzing and validating the requirements through the project's Advisory Boards. The feedback obtained from the proposed questionnaire for requirements validation are presented in this part and conclusions are drawn afterwards.

Finally, the fourth part of the deliverable deals with the three Targets of Evaluation (ToEs), namely, the Business, Technical, and Sectorial. Their descriptions and the respective validated requirements are provided in this section.

Two appendixes are included in the document. The first one gives information on a glossary that forms the basis of the concepts used in the project, while the second one gives details regarding the first workshop organized with the Advisory Boards at the end of the first six months of the project.

DISCLAIMER: The document was submitted for revision to the EU Commission and is awaiting review and acceptance. Full access to its content will become available after this.